

The Reduction of the Group $-\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{-CCl}_3$.

Part I

BY

ANDREW NORMAN MELDRUM

AND

RUPCHAND LILARAM ALIMCHANDANI

The reduction of trichloromethyl carbinols was studied by Jocitsch (J. Russ. Chem. Soc., 1898, 30, 920-924) and Jocitsch and Favorsky, (*ibid.*, 990-1003)¹ with the result that the products were found to be derivatives of dichloroethylene: for instance, phenyl trichloromethyl carbinol gave dichloro-styrene:

The reduction was carried out in boiling alcoholic solution and the best results were obtained by taking, not the carbinol itself, but its acetyl derivative, and using zinc in the form of shavings. (Jocitsch and Favorsky, *loc. cit.*).

Jocitsch's method of reduction leads to the conversion of the group $-\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{CCl}_3$ into $-\text{CH:CCl}_2$ and of $>\text{C}(\text{OH})\text{CCl}_3$ into $>\text{C:CCl}_2$. Following on this change chlorine atoms were sometimes replaced by hydrogen. Thus acetone-chloroform on reduction gave three products, namely, dichloro*iso*-butylene, *isocrotylic* chloride, and *isobutylene*:

¹ The original papers are not easily accessible and are known to us only in abstract. For the papers cited above see *Jour. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 76, I, 748; 786: for numerous papers on the synthesis and reduction of trichloromethyl carbinols that were published by Jocitsch from 1902 to 1906, see *loc. cit.*, 1914, 106, i, (under the spelling Jocitsch).

For the present purpose it is not necessary to consider tertiary alcohols that contain the group $>C(OH) \cdot CCl_3$. The scope of this paper is limited to secondary alcohols containing the group $-CH(OH) \cdot CCl_3$; this group can be reduced to $-CH : CCl_2$ as Jocitsch's work has proved :—

The authors observed indications that the group $-CH(OH)CCl_3$, under different conditions from those employed by Jocitsch, can be reduced to $-CH_2 \cdot CHCl_2$, the reducing agent that was employed was zinc dust and acetic acid. A condensation product of *p*-cresotic acid and chloral, having the formula $C_{12}H_8O_4Cl_6$, was converted by reduction into the substance $C_{10}H_{10}O_3Cl_2$. This was explained as follows :—the substance of formula $C_{12}H_8O_4Cl_6$ contains the heterocyclic ring

which is hydrolysed to

and chloral and then the reduction proceeds thus :—
 $-CH(OH)CCl_3 + 4H = -CH_2 \cdot CHCl_2 + H_2O + HCl$. (T., 1921, 119, 204). The reduction product was easily obtained and it appeared that the group $-CHCl_2$ is almost inert towards the reducing agent.

Whilst this explanation is sufficient and satisfactory as far as it goes, it is true that it turns into an intermediate product, which was not isolated, and that better evidence might be forthcoming on the subject. The

authors have made a beginning with the study of the numerous compounds that contain the group $-\text{CH}(\text{OH})\cdot\text{CCl}_3$ and have found various cases in which this group is changed into $-\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CHCl}_2$. The cases reported in this paper can be classified as follows:—

- I. DERIVATIVES OF *m*-CRESOTIC ACID;
- II. $\gamma\gamma\gamma$ -TRICHLORO— β —HYDROXY-BUTYRIC ACID;
- III. DERIVATIVES OF UREA, THIOUREA, URÉTHANE AND URETHYLANE.

I. DERIVATIVES OF *m*-CRESOTIC ACID.

*3-methoxy - 6 - α - hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl-*p*-toluic acid.*¹

The solution obtained by shaking together 3-methoxy-*p*-toluic acid (58 grams), chloral hydrate (74 grams) and sulphuric acid (97 per cent., 275 c. c.) was kept for three days and then poured over ice. A white deposit was formed which was crystallised from glacial acetic acid and then for analysis, from acetone: prisms mp. $236-237^\circ$, with effervescence. (Found: $\text{Cl}=33.78$; equivalent = 312.7 ; $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_3$ requires $\text{Cl}=33.95$; equivalent = 313.5).

The *calcium salt* (prismatic needles) crystallises with 10 molecules of water of crystallisation. Two different samples were analysed. (Found: $\text{Ca}=4.74$; 4.74 ; $(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_3)_2 \cdot \text{Ca} \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires $\text{Ca}=4.74$ per cent.)

The *acetyl derivative* (crystalline powder) melts at $203-204^\circ$. (Found: equivalent = 355.5 ; $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_5\text{Cl}_3$ requires equivalent = 355.5).

¹ The authors, by work that will be described in a later paper, have proved this substance to have the constitution ascribed to it above.

3-methoxy-6 ββ-dichloroethyl p-toluic acid.

To the hot solution of the trichloromethyl carbinol (2 grams) in acetic acid (10 c. c.), zinc dust (2.5 grams) was added little by little; the heating was continued for about 15 minutes. The liquid was filtered and water was added to the filtrate: white leaflets were obtained which after crystallisation from methyl alcohol melted at 166-167°. (Found: Cl=26.86; equivalent = 262; $C_{11}H_{12}O_3Cl_2$, requires Cl=26.96; equivalent=263).

The authors have studied also a substance that is produced in the condensation of chloral with *m*-cresotic acid. As the main product of this condensation Schleussner and Voswinckel (*Annalen.*, 1921, 422, 111) obtained amorphous material, from which, by a series of changes, that ended with methylation of the phenolic group, they obtained the methyl ether of γ -coccinic acid (Meldrum. T., 1911, 99, 1712). The amorphous material, the authors find, contains at least one crystalline substance formed according to the equation:

On reduction it yields a crystalline substance $C_{12}H_{12}O_3Cl_4$. This change can be explained thus: the substance $C_{14}H_8O_3Cl_3$ is $C_8H_5O_2(C_4H_2O_2Cl_3)-CH(OH) \cdot CCl_3$, that is, it contains the cresotic acid residue and (1) the heterocyclic ring that is present in the *p*-cresotic acid derivative already mentioned; (2) the group- $CH(OH) \cdot CCl_3$ that is present in the chloral derivative of the methyl ether of *m*-cresotic acid. When the heterocyclic ring is hydrolysed the product contains two- $CH(OH) \cdot CCl_3$ groups that can be reduced.

Condensation of m-cresotic acid and chloral.

The solution obtained by shaking together *m*-cresotic acid (16 grams), chloral hydrate (50 grams) and sulphuric acid (97 per cent., 100 c.c.) was kept for three days and then poured on ice. A gelatinous mass separated which was washed and dried. When it was dissolved in dilute acetic acid, a small amount of a crystalline powder separated. This was re-crystallised from methyl alcohol; glistening plates mp. 211-212°. (Found: Cl=55.20; $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{O}_5\text{Cl}_2$ requires Cl=55.38 per cent.).

Reduction of the substance $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{O}_5\text{Cl}_2$

To the hot solution of the substance $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{O}_5\text{Cl}_2$ (2 grams) in glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) zinc dust (5 grams) was added in small amount. The mixture was boiled for 15 minutes, and then filtered. When the filtrate was diluted with water, a substance separated in white leaflets. It was recrystallised from benzene for analysis: mp. 164-165° (Found Cl=41.3; $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5\text{Cl}_4$ requires Cl=41.0 per cent.).

The *calcium* salt crystallises in needles. (Found: Ca=5.54; $(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_5\text{Cl}_4)_2\text{Ca}$ requires Ca=5.49 per cent.).

II. $\text{CCl}_3\text{.CHOH.CH}_2\text{.COOH}$ $\gamma\gamma\gamma$ -Trichloro- β -hydroxy-butyrlic acid
 $\text{CHCl}_2\text{.CH}_2\text{.CH}_2\text{.COOH}$ $\gamma\gamma$ -Dichloro butyrlic acid.

After preliminary experiments had been made on the reduction of $\gamma\gamma\gamma$ -trichloro- β -hydroxy-butyrlic acid and of its ethyl ester the reduction was carried out using the methyl ester. (mp. 65-66°; Auwers and Schmidt (Ber., 1913, 46, 487) give 61-62°).

The methyl ester (30 grams) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (100 c.c.); the solution was stirred mechanically whilst zinc dust (15 grams) was gradually added at such a rate that the temperature of the mixture did not

rise above 60°. The process lasted about an hour. Zinc acetate and unchanged zinc were removed by filtration and the filtrate when diluted with water, yielded a heavy oil (16 grams). This oil was dissolved in ether, washed with water, dried and distilled under reduced pressure: bp. 95-100°/36 mm. It is an unstable substance and was not obtained pure even by repeated distillation. (Found: Cl=39.2; $C_5H_8O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl=41.5; $C_5H_7O_2Cl_3$ requires Cl=48.1 per cent.). It was hydrolysed by shaking a mixture of the oil (5 grams) with a 10 per cent. sodium hydroxide solution (50 c.c.) for about 10 minutes, when the oil disappeared. On acidification of the solution a solid was obtained (0.5 gram) which was purified by crystallisation from water: shining leaflets mp. 103-104°. (Found: Cl=45.20; $C_4H_8O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl=45.21 per cent.).

This acid and its esters will be investigated further. The acid itself is stable whilst the esters and the salts are unstable. The methyl and ethyl esters at ordinary temperature give off pungent vapours, and on distillation there is always a residue that crystallises. When the acid is treated with sodium hydroxide solution, there are unmistakable signs that the $-CHCl_2$ group is hydrolysed: this accounts for the small yield of the acid that was obtained when the methyl ester was hydrolysed.

III. Derivatives of urea, thiourea, urethane and urethylane

Dichloralurea has been obtained by Jacobsen (*Annalen.*, 1871, 157, 247). This substance (3 grams) being sparingly soluble in glacial acetic acid was suspended in that liquid (35 c.c.). Zinc dust (4 grams) was added with the same precautions as were observed in the case just mentioned. The reaction was slow; even after continuing the

process for about four hours, zinc (2.5 grams) remained unattacked. The filtered liquid after dilution gave needle shaped crystals (0.5 gram). The substance was re-crystallised from alcohol for analysis: mp. 222° with decomposition. (Found: Cl=55.86; C₅H₈ON₂Cl₄ requires Cl=55.85 per cent.).

This was prepared by heating a mixture of thiourea (7 grams) and chloral (32 grams); vigorous reaction took place. After washing the product with hot water, it was crystallised from a mixture of ether and benzene: crystalline powder mp. 150-151° with decomposition. (Found: Cl=57.31; C₅H₈O₂N₂SCl₆ requires Cl=57.35 per cent.)

The reduction product, namely, *tetrachlorodiethylthiourea* was obtained in exactly the same manner as the corresponding urea derivative. From benzene it crystallises in lustrous leaflets mp. 162-163° with decomposition. (Found: Cl=52.72; S=11.73; C₅H₈SN₂Cl₄ requires Cl=52.50; S=11.87 per cent.).

CHCl₂.CH₂.NH.COOC₂H₅ Dichloroethyl-urethane

Chloral urethane was prepared by Bischoff's method (*Ber.* 1874, 7, 6314). It melts at 106-108° (Bischoff gives 103°). To the solution of this substance (38 grams) in glacial acetic acid (150 c. c.) zinc dust (24 grams) was added with the same precautions as before. The reaction mixture was filtered and ice was added to the filtrate. An oil separated at first which crystallised when it was cooled by a freezing mixture. The solid was separated using a funnel cooled by ice and was dissolved in ether, washed with very dilute sodium carbonate solution, dried and distilled under reduced pressure: bp. 125-128°/23 m.m.

The solid melts at about 13°. (Found : Cl=37.54; C₅H₉O₂NCl₂ requires Cl=38.13 per cent.).

CCl₂CH(OH).NH.COOCH₃ Chloral urethylane

Urethylane (156 grams) and chloral (96 grams) dissolved rapidly in conc. hydrochloric acid (96 c. c.). The solid product separated in about half an hour. To the filtrate, chloral (48 grams) was added when another crop of the same substance was obtained. A fresh charge of chloral (24 grams) was again added. The collected yield of the condensation product was 267 grams. From chloroform it crystallises in rhombic plates : mp. 125-128°. (Found : Cl=47.80; C₄H₉O₂NCl₂ requires Cl=47.84 per cent.).

CHCl₂.CH₂.NH.COOCH₃ Dichloroethyl-urethylane

Chloral urethylane (132 grams) was dissolved in acetic acid (530 c. c.). Zinc dust (76 grams) was added with the same precautions as before. The filtrate after dilution with water gave needle shaped crystals which when recrystallised from alcohol melted at 90-93°. (Found : Cl=41.10; C₄H₇O₂NCl₂ requires Cl=41.23 per cent.).

The solution obtained by dissolving dichloroethyl urethylane (2 grams) in dry ether (20 c. c.) was saturated with dry HCl. After keeping for two days, it was slowly evaporated on the water bath when a syrupy liquid was obtained. When dissolved in hot benzene it crystallises in clusters of tiny needles : mp. 118-120°. (Found : Cl=29.38; C₃H₄O₂NCl requires Cl=29.18 per cent.).

Part of the expense of this investigation was defrayed by a grant from the Syndicate of the University of Bombay.

Work on the substances that are described in this paper and on other trichloromethyl carbinols is being continued.

DEPARTMENT OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY,
THE ROYAL INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BOMBAY.

[*Received 3rd February, 1925*].
